

SELF-HEALING OF A FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITE MATERIAL USING METAL TRIFLATES AS CATALYTIC CURING AGENTS

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Abstract

Metal triflates are employed as catalytic curing agents for ring-opening polymerisation (ROP) of epoxy resin to facilitate self-healing in a high performance, fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composite material. Laminates manufactured using existing industrial methods contain an embedded bio-inspired series of microvascular channels for the delivery of self-healing agent to exposed fractured crack planes. Thermal cure analysis and mechanical testing is employed to characterise the self-healed polymer by using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and a tapered double cantilever beam (TDCB) test specimen geometry. After initial Mode I crack opening displacement unloaded samples are injected with Lewis acid catalysed epoxy self-healing agent (SHA) and left to cure. Strong adhesive compatibility with the host matrix confers full recovery of mechanical properties (>99% healing).

1. Introduction

Design considerations and material usage are changing significantly in transport sectors to ultimately achieve lightweight structures in order to improve energy efficiency, reduce fuel consumption, increase range, sustain current costs and incorporate sustainable materials [1-4]. Over the past few years, aerospace, automotive and chemical industries have led the development and implementation of lightweight fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) materials, focusing on adapting and rendering existing and new design envelopes to implement new materials [5] and incorporate novel technologies [6].

Working with relatively 'new' materials involves detailed consideration of pre-existing operating parameters that can result in certain design challenges [7]. Preventing propagation of sub-surface structural micro-cracking in FRP materials leads to imposed conservative design philosophies that can significantly limit the inherent lightweight nature of such a material. A system capable of restoring mechanical efficiency after damage formation, such as self-healing, has the potential to reduce inspection and maintenance costs (i.e. non-destructive testing (NDT)) and eliminate challenging, costly and complicated repairs to realise lighter composite structures.

Catastrophic failure of a FRP composite component can result from micro-cracking as cracks rapidly propagate throughout the laminated structure. For example, this damage can manifest itself as fibre-resin interfacial debonding, occur between stacked laminae, or arise from manufacturing defects, causing stress concentrations which lead to the onset of premature component failure [8]. The focus of this research builds on the further development and implementation of previously developed self-healing agents by Coope *et al.* [9], to achieve a self-healing FRP material using typical industrial composite manufacturing techniques. Utilising this system in FRP composite materials has the potential to address the issues of internal damage highlighted above and prolong the useful life of materials currently difficult and expensive to repair or recycle using traditional methods [10].

Over the past 10 years, Bond, Trask and co-workers have extensively researched a bio-inspired vasculature approach [11] to self-healing in high performance thermoset composite materials, to

satisfy the requirements for delivering high healing agent volumes to areas with severe internal damage. Hollow glass fibres (HGFs) [12-16] and microvascular channels [17-20] have successfully demonstrated reliable methods for self-healing agent (SHA) delivery to damaged areas through multiple mixed-mode testing. Norris *et al.* have further developed this concept with the stimuli triggered delivery of a pre-mixed commercial epoxy SHA into an aerospace grade composite material, when subject to low energy impact damage, to recover compression after impact (CAI) strength [21-23].

The SHAs implemented in this study offer significant improvements over alternative well documented self-healing systems, for example those employing Grubbs' catalyst [24], polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS)/di-*n*-butyltin dilaurate (DBTL) [25] and epoxy/maleimide [26]. These improvements include host matrix compatibility, catalytic activity under mild conditions, relatively low cost and toxicity, high stability, commercial availability and system tailorability. In this study, we have further developed the solid phase scandium(III) triflate-epoxy system, considered other similar metal triflate catalysts and solvents to initiate and expedite epoxide ring-opening polymerisation (ROP).

The most suitable polymer-solvent formulation to achieve a significant recovery of material properties in FRP epoxy-based composite materials was initially identified by using thermal cure analysis and bulk polymer mechanical testing. This study demonstrated the system's potential and tailorability as SHA can be successfully delivered by a variety of ways, including microvascular networks, HGFs or microcapsules.

Herein, is a demonstration of a self-healing FRP composite material using a double cantilever beam (DCB) coupon specimen geometry, facilitated by the delivery of novel epoxy-metal triflate SHAs via embedded microvascular channels. The focus of this research was a 'proof of concept' study for fracture repair in FRP test specimens using conventional industrial composite material manufacturing techniques and the aforementioned novel SHAs. As reported below, results have shown a significant recovery of fracture toughness (>99%) that matches the initial fracture mechanism of the host FRP material and an ability to create a repair with superior toughness than the original host polymer matrix material.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The catalytic activity of scandium(III) triflate ($\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$) with an oligomeric DGEBA epoxy resin (EPON 828) was investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). A number of variables were identified for analysis such as solvent quantity and type, blended with EPON 828 resin, catalyst loading and catalyst type.

Dynamic experiments in the range 0-250 °C at a rate of 10 °C/min used an initial medium (M) catalyst loading [3.125 pph]. Cure onset temperatures for ROP of EPON 828 containing 10 wt% EPA (E10) and 25 wt% EPA (E25) gave values of 34.6 °C and 49.8 °C respectively, a significant reduction when compared with the solvent free EPON 828 derivative (81.6 °C) (**Figure 1**). Modifying the catalyst concentration to higher (H) [6.25 pph] and lower (L) [1.5625 pph] loadings confirmed predictions of a retrospective decrease (27.9 °C) and increase (79.3 °C) of cure onset temperature for E10 Sc derivatives.

Furthermore, a room temperature ionic liquid (RTIL), 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoro-borate (EMIM BF_4), was evaluated as a co-solvent to achieve a lower cure onset temperature. DSC runs using a (M) catalyst loading, 25 wt% EMIM BF_4 and 12.5 wt% EMIM BF_4 : 12.5 wt% EPA solvent gave onset cure temperatures of 11.1 °C and 24.2 °C respectively. This is a reduction of 38.7 °C and 25.6 °C, respectively, in comparison the E25 Sc (M) derivative. Therefore, cure duration is significantly reduced at ambient and marginally elevated temperatures.

Alternative metal triflates such as aluminium(III) triflate ($\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$) and copper(II) triflate ($\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$) were also investigated as commercially readily available and lower cost alternatives to $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$. Experiments containing $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$ with a E25 monomer-solvent solution resulted in similar cure onset temperatures to $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ for all three catalyst loadings. However, a reduction in solvent quantity (i.e. from E25 to E10) reduces the activity of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ and more significantly for $\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$ (**Table 1**). This is attributed to catalyst solubility in EPA solvent. Therefore, $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ and $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ catalysts were pursued as SHAs in this study.

This DSC study was carried out to identify the most reliable low temperature or autonomous ROP-based self-healing system by considering the

catalytic activity of metal triflates and EPON 828 with respect to solvent and catalyst loadings. Solvent inclusion in a non-solvated system has a significant effect on achieving low temperature curing. Increasing solvent concentration further, for example, from 25 wt% to 50 wt% dilutes this effect due to increased mobility and reduced contact of active sites in the reagent mixture. Furthermore, increasing catalyst loading and blending solvents with a RTIL also significantly reduces the onset temperature for polymerisation where catalyst solubility is permitted.

2.2. TDCB Fracture Testing

Mechanical testing of the cured bulk self-healed polymer was carried out using the previously documented modified TDCB test specimen arrangement to initially identify a suitable polymer formulation in order to achieve the required self-healing functionality in FRP composite materials [9,28]. Pre-mixed solutions of the respective polymer formulations were cast in silicone moulds to form the central trench section and cured at 45 °C for 24 hours. Subsequently, the main specimen geometry was cast using EPON 828 and diethylenetriamine (DETA). TDCB specimens were initiated with a sharp razor blade and tested to failure.

Three polymer formulations were evaluated, each with varied solvent quantity and type. This included Sc(OTf)₃ at a medium (M) concentration [Sc (M)], EPA at 10 wt% [E10 Sc (M)], 25 wt% [E25 Sc (M)] and equal quantities of EPA (12.5 wt%) and EMIM BF₄ (12.5 wt%) [EMIM EPA Sc (M)]. From a total of 5 test specimens, E10 Sc (M) gave average initial fracture and displacement values of, 92.3 N and 0.95 mm. E25 Sc (M) gave average initial fracture and displacement values of, 107.2 N and 1.53 mm. Finally, EMIM EPA Sc (M) gave average initial fracture and displacement values of, 86.7 N and 0.89 mm.

The fracture mechanism for E10 Sc (M) and EMIM EPA Sc (M) derivatives was typical of thermoset epoxy resin, being brittle in nature (**Figure 2**). In comparison, E25 Sc (M) specimens failed in a ductile manner due in part to the solvent acting as a plasticiser in the host matrix. As discussed in the previous section, EMIM EPA Sc (M) containing the RTIL EMIM BF₄ as a co-solvent benefitted from an increased cure rate, reduced viscosity and comparable failure load when compared to the E10 Sc (M) derivative.

Therefore, inclusion of a higher wt% of EPA solvent resulted in a ductile failure mechanism, an important parameter when healing such an inherently brittle host material.

2.3. DCB Fracture Testing

Self-healing performance was assessed in an FRP material using a microvascular double cantilever beam (DCB) test specimen arrangement as developed by Norris *et al.* [19]. This method is based on the ASTM D5528-01 standard for Mode I crack opening displacement of FRP composite materials [27], a unidirectional (UD) glass fibre reinforced epoxy composite (HexPly 913, Hexcel Composites) was manufactured with two 0.5 mm longitudinal vasculae along the central mid-plane to facilitate external self-healing agent injection (**Figure 3**). Mode I crack opening displacement has been thoroughly investigated to provide successful crack-microvasculae interconnectivity to allow SHAs to wet out the crack planes and re-bond fractured surfaces [19,20]. Test specimens were initially fractured, unloaded from the test machine, allowed to heal and subsequently re-tested to failure following the same protocol.

Mode I strain energy release rate, G_{Ic} , values were calculated from load (P), displacement (δ), delamination length (a) and specimen width (b) values using the modified beam theory (MBT) method (**Equation 1**). As the beam is not perfectly built-in, rotation may occur at the delamination front; therefore a correction factor, Δ , is incorporated which treats the DCB specimen as if it contained a slightly longer delamination ($a + |\Delta|$). Δ was calculated experimentally by generating a least squares plot of the cube root of compliance, $C^{1/3}$, as a function of delamination length [27]. Healing efficiencies (ζ) were calculated for each individual test specimen using the initial ($P_{Initial}$) and healed (P_{Healed}) fracture load values (**Equation 2**) and crack initiation fracture toughness values in terms of the strain energy release rate (G_{Ic}) (**Equation 3**). The data presented here corresponds to average data points obtained from at least 5 replicates.

$$G_{Ic} = 3P\delta / 2b(a + |\Delta|) \quad (1)$$

$$\zeta_{LOAD} = P_{Healed} / P_{Initial} \quad (2)$$

$$\zeta_{G_{Ic}} = G_{Ic\ Healed} / G_{Ic\ Initial} \quad (3)$$

Specimen derivatives including SHA reagent combinations, healing conditions and delivery methods used in the DCB testing are outlined in **Table 2**.

2.3.1. Benchmark Commercial Healing System

A commercially available epoxy-amine thermoset, consisting of EPON 828 and diethylenetriamine (E25 DETA), was selected as a benchmark resin system for this study. EPA solvent (25 pph) was added to reduce viscosity and aid resin infusion via the microvascular channels [21]. Initial fracture toughness testing of five baseline FRP specimens at a displacement rate of 2 mm/min resulted in progressive crack propagation along the mid-plane at an average load of 27.2 N; a failure mode typical of Mode I loaded UD test specimens. An average strain energy release rate (G_{Ic}) of 218 J/m² for delamination initiation was derived from these results.

The fractured test specimens were subsequently prepared for healing by applying one-sided adhesive release tape (63 micron thickness), 1.5 mm across the crack plane from the perimeter edges of fractured surfaces, and areas to be non-bonded (i.e. starter pre-crack region of the specimen). This is primarily to constrain the injected SHA to the crack plane and prevent leaching during cure. Furthermore, the void (126 micron thickness) created between the fractured surfaces, by the presence of the tape, is representative of that formed when internal barely visible impact damage (BVID) is generated in FRP composite materials after an impact. This feature has recently been characterised and investigated using micro-CT [29].

The E25 DETA pre-mixed SHA was introduced via the edge-located vasculature and left to cure in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications (7 days, 25 °C). The SHA was allowed to wet out the crack plane with no external intervention to influence SHA distribution on the fracture surfaces. This factor is critical in trying to replicate the likely SHA delivery mechanism in large-scale FRP components.

Healed specimens achieved an average recovery of greater than 95% initial fracture toughness and 86% peak load. The average healed failure load value corresponded to 23.5 N.

2.3.2. Low Temperature (45 °C) Healing System

A low temperature healing cure cycle consisting of 45 °C for 24 hours was selected as being easily achievable during existing maintenance schedules for a FRP composite structure. Furthermore, results from DSC thermal cure analysis highlighted that healing with a medium catalyst loading (M) [3.125 pph] is achievable at temperatures marginally above ambient. In addition, the effect of different quantities of EPA solvent on the ability to infuse SHA and the resulting polymer and mechanical performance was investigated by considering E10 and E25 monomer solutions.

Sc(OTf)₃ [3.125 pph] combined with E10 monomer (E10 Sc (M)) achieved a healed average recovery of >119% initial fracture toughness and 104% peak load. Therefore, the material properties of the resulting healed polymer are at least equal to the material properties of the host matrix. If damage were to occur in the same region it is likely that the crack would deviate away from the healed region and propagate through the existing host matrix. Due to the small quantity of solvent present, the resulting polymer is inherently brittle, similar to most cured epoxide materials, resulting in a 'sawtooth' load-displacement plot (**Figure 4**).

In comparison, mechanical testing of the same polymer formulation using E25 monomer (E25 Sc (M)) revealed a very different fracture pattern. Due to the high boiling point (229 °C) of the EPA solvent, it effectively acts as a plasticiser in the healed polymer. Therefore, a ductile load-displacement plot is observed which is similar to the initial fracture response of the host material (**Figure 5**). This also results in an average of 26% and 81% increase in peak load and fracture toughness healing efficiencies, respectively, when compared to the lower solvated derivative, E10 Sc (M) (**Figure 6**). Additionally, in this study, environmental testing has confirmed this as not being a transitional state.

To consider the end-user usability of such a system, experimentation into the catalyst loading was sought to establish if healing efficiencies could be maintained at higher (H) [6.25 pph] and lower (L) [1.5625 pph] catalyst concentrations. Therefore, test specimens were healed with double and half catalyst concentrations of the E25 Sc (M) derivative. From five test replicates, an increase of 46% healed peak load and 152% healed fracture toughness was observed when doubling catalyst concentration (E25 Sc (H)). Subsequently, test specimens (5) healed with a reduced catalyst concentration (E25 Sc (L))

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achieved comparable results to E25 Sc (M), with a 1% healed load decrease and a 22% healed fracture toughness decrease. When taking into account the standard deviation of these values it can be concluded that a reduction in catalyst concentration can achieve comparable healing efficiencies at the point of delamination initiation. Therefore, a healthy reserve factor could be applied to E25 Sc (M) in an industrial application to achieve a minimum healing efficiency value in line with E25 Sc (L) test specimen results.

As confirmed from the DSC results, $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ has a similar reactivity although a slight reduction in solubility in comparison to $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$. Therefore, E10 and E25 $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ 3.125 pph (E10 Al (M), E25 Al (M)) were employed as healing agents to establish if similar mechanical properties could be achieved by using this significantly more economically viable catalyst.

From a total of five test replicates, E10 Al (M) specimens achieved a marginal decrease in healing efficiency for fracture toughness (-10%) and peak load (-6%) when compared to $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$. Similarly, E25 Al (M) specimens achieved a decrease in healing efficiency for fracture toughness (-59%) and peak load (-19%). Therefore, additional catalyst could be employed to achieve higher healing efficiencies and improved reactivity than $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$, but at a much lower cost.

Lastly, an alternative solvent was considered to establish if it could contribute to or influence the overall structural integrity of the host matrix. The RTIL, EMIM BF_4 was investigated as a co-solvent with EPA to accelerate the curing kinetics of the self-healing polymer by increasing catalyst reactivity. It has recently been documented [30,31] that RTILs can act as thermally latent initiators for curing epoxy resin at significantly elevated temperatures (>100 °C). In this study, addition of metal triflate catalysts resulted in a reduction of onset cure temperature to achieve ambient temperature curing within 24 hours.

DCB specimens healed at 45 °C for 24 hours with an EMIM EPA Sc (M) polymer formulation (12.5 wt% EPA; 12.5 wt% EMIM BF_4) gave comparable results to the E25 DETA ambient cured derivative. A healing efficiency of 83% and 71% for fracture toughness and peak load resulted.

2.3.3. High Temperature (80 °C) Healing System

Curing of $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ healed specimens at a higher temperature was investigated to establish if

significant improvements in healing efficiencies could be achieved. The most promising formulations (E10 Sc (M) and E25 Sc (M)) from the low temperature study were healed at 80 °C for 24 hours and subsequently re-tested at ambient temperature. From a total of five test replicates, E10 Sc (M) specimens achieved a negligible change in healing efficiency for fracture toughness (-7%) and peak load (+2%) when compared to the lower temperature counterpart.

In comparison, healed E25 Sc (M) specimens achieved on average a 29% and 106% increase in peak load and fracture toughness healing efficiencies. Therefore, the average healed peak load value (44.2 N) was significantly higher than the initial fracture peak load value (27.8 N), resulting in an overall healing efficiency of 159%.

2.3.4. Ambient Temperature Healing System

To achieve an autonomous self-healing composite material, test specimens were infused with a pre-mixed solution and left to cure at ambient temperature (RT) for 7 days. This healing scheme is typical of ambient temperature cured epoxy systems. The derivatives demonstrated in this study include E10 Sc (M), E25 Sc (M) and E25 Sc (H) as these were highlighted as the best overall analogues in the 45 °C / 24 hour healing scheme. DSC analysis of the resultant SHP showed complete cure in this time period.

Firstly, E25 Sc (M) was evaluated, giving a load healing efficiency of 113% and a fracture toughness healing efficiency of 121%. Comparing these values with the 45 °C cured derivative reveals a 17% reduction in load healing efficiency and a 79% reduction in fracture toughness healing efficiency. Furthermore, these ambient temperature results are comparable with E25 Al (M) healed at 45 °C for 24 hours. On increasing catalyst concentrations the maximum load (127%) and fracture toughness (185%) healing efficiencies become comparable to E25 Sc (L) healed at 45 °C for 24 hours with values of 129% and 178%, respectively.

Lastly, evaluating E10 Sc (M) healed at ambient temperature reveals a decrease in healing efficiency of 32% for maximum load (72%) and a decrease in healing efficiency of 35% for fracture toughness (84%). Therefore, it was observed that to maintain healing efficiencies close to the fracture toughness of the host matrix at ambient temperature, a higher quantity of solvent (E25) is required. This is

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attributed to reagent migration within the solvated healing polymer during cure.

2.3.5. Autonomous Delivery System

An autonomous delivery system was investigated to demonstrate self-healing functionality where separate solutions of $\text{Sc}(\text{OTf})_3$ -EPA and EPON 828-EPA were introduced via parallel microvascular networks (AUTO E25 Sc (M) [AUTO]). The total solvent and catalyst loading was analogous to E25 Sc (M) and cured at 45 °C for 48 hours. A longer cure time was prescribed to account for catalyst infusion throughout the monomer solution. Ultimately, if this were to occur in a pressurised system the rate of autonomous mixing would greatly increase and would, therefore, be comparable to derivatives healed using a pre-mixed solution.

From five test replicates, healing efficiencies for load and fracture toughness at delamination initiation were 100% and 88%, respectively. However, as the extension was increased from this point the load carrying capability also increased until a reduction in maximum load was observed at ~20 mm extension. Therefore, AUTO specimens showed a higher degree of ductility to achieve a maximum load comparable to the host matrix at >100% increase in extension. Therefore, the fracture toughness was considerably higher (2-3 times) at the point of maximum load than observed for pre-mixed samples.

Due to the challenges of curing an unmixed polymer solution at low temperature, EMIM BF_4 was added to the self-healing polymer formulation to expedite reaction cure kinetics and to achieve a cured polymeric material with a comparable stiffness to the host matrix. Retesting the polymer after healing at 45 °C for 24 hours - a twofold reduction in healing duration when compared with the pure EPA derivative, gave healing efficiencies for load and fracture toughness of 98% and 104% respectively. This is a significant improvement to healing performance and in creating a polymer with a comparable stiffness to the host matrix.

3. Discussion

The previously demonstrated DGEBA-EPA + scandium triflate catalyst self-healing system was further developed and refined to facilitate self-healing in high performance FRP composite materials. By incorporating bio-inspired vascular

channels into the material, autonomous delivery of healing agent was possible without having a detrimental effect on the host material mechanical properties.

Evaluating the mechanical properties for solvated metal triflate-initiated epoxide polymers was sought by using a FRP composite material DCB geometry. In total, three EPA solvent concentrations/formulations, three healing temperatures, three catalyst loadings, two metal triflate catalysts and two delivery methods were investigated in order to achieve high performance healing using a low temperature-short healing time protocol. Solvent concentration had the greatest influence with regards to the resultant fracture of the healed polymer. Although a cohesive failure in all specimens was observed, the inclusion of a low solvent quantity (i.e. E10 derivatives) facilitated a brittle fracture whereas E25 derivatives with more solvent failed in a ductile manner, similar to the host material behaviour. Both solvated derivatives achieved comparable peak load values at the point of delamination initiation.

Achieving self-healing in FRP composite materials at ambient temperature, restoring mechanical properties comparable to the host matrix, was the predominant focus for this study. Similar to the findings for test specimens healed at low temperature, there was a direct correlation between solvent quantity and fracture pattern and also between catalyst loading and healing efficiencies. This is attributed to the solvent acting as a plasticiser, enhancing ductility and facilitating SHA migration between fracture surfaces to achieve high cross-linking density from metal triflate-initiated epoxide sites. Healing at a higher temperature does not induce a significant increase in healing performance over specimens healed at low or ambient temperatures when considering the extra energy required.

E25 Sc (M) was highlighted as the best overall specimen derivative to achieve reliable healing performance equal or greater than the host material mechanical properties. Therefore, a medium catalyst loading [3.125 pph] was chosen as a representative value to evaluate $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ as a catalytic curing agent for FRP composite materials. This also represented a cost effective, active quantity capable of curing at low and ambient temperatures. Modified catalyst loadings were limited to E25 Sc derivatives cured at 45 °C and ambient temperatures due to reduced solubility of $\text{Al}(\text{OTf})_3$ in EPA solvent. Furthermore, healing temperatures were limited to

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45 °C, 80 °C and ambient temperature in line with previously investigated self-healing systems and the aim of this study, i.e. to maintain minimum external energy input for healing to occur.

4. Conclusion

Aerospace-grade FRP composite materials were self-healed via injection of EPON 828 and Lewis-acid metal triflate catalysts. A 26% minimum healing efficiency increase was observed for implementing these SHAs compared with the commercial-based EPON 828/DETA system. DCB test specimens were fabricated with 0.5 mm microvascular channels as an integral non-detrimental network for the delivery of SHAs to damaged regions in the material. Test specimen derivatives independently considered monomer-solvent content, healing temperature, catalyst type and catalyst loading.

E25 Sc healed test specimens achieved a minimum healing efficiency of 129% via the injection of a pre-mixed solution at 45 °C, demonstrating full recovery of fracture toughness. Ultimately, autonomous curing was one of the main objectives for this self-healing system. Thus, curing at ambient temperature provided a minimum healing efficiency of 113% for this same system. A modest increase of 30% healing efficiency resulted from healing at 80 °C when compared with healing at low temperature. The highest healing efficiency was achieved by introducing a higher catalyst concentration to E25 Sc cured at 45 °C. This resulted in a 176% load recovery and a 352% fracture toughness recovery. Furthermore, an autonomous delivery method facilitated by infusion of separate Sc(OTf)₃-EPA and EPON 828 solutions via parallel vasculature achieved a 100% load recovery and 88% fracture toughness at delamination initiation. Inclusion of EMIM BF₄ as a co-solvent to healing agents delivered autonomously resulted in healing efficiencies of fracture toughness and maximum load to 98% and 104%, respectively, after a reduced cure duration of 24 hours.

Healing a load bearing high performance material remains one of the key challenges in developing and implementing self-healing materials. In this study we have successfully demonstrated high healing efficiencies for fracture toughness recovery at modest raised and ambient temperatures in a FRP composite material manufactured using conventional industrial methods. This research further demonstrates the application and tailorability

of the underpinning chemistry of this self-healing system across a variety of delivery systems. Therefore when coupled with structural health monitoring (SHM) systems and a pressurised pumping system it is potentially capable of multiple healing cycles and being truly autonomous in nature [23].

5. Experimental Section

Materials:

Ethyl phenylacetate (EPA), diethylenetriamine (DETA, (NH₂CH₂CH₂)₂NH), scandium(III) triflate (Sc(OTf)₃), aluminium(III) triflate (Al(OTf)₃), copper(II) triflate (Cu(OTf)₂) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EMIM BF₄) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received. EPON 828 was purchased from Polysciences, Inc.. E-glass/epoxy pre-impregnated tape was purchased from Hexcel.

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

Samples for the DSC experiments were prepared by mixing catalyst (Sc(OTf)₃, Al(OTf)₃ or Cu(OTf)₂) at the prescribed loading with EPON 828 and EPA solvent and/or EMIM BF₄. The following wt% of EPA was added to EPON 828; 0 wt% (EPON), 10 wt% (E10) or 25 wt% (E25). EMIM EPA Sc (M) comprised of 12.5% wt% EPA and 12.5 wt% EMIM BF₄. The solution was thoroughly mixed at ambient temperature and quickly transferred (approximately 10 mg) to aluminium Tzero hermetic pans. A TA Instruments Q200 DSC was used to study non-isothermal curing via dynamic scans. Samples were heated from 0 to 250 °C at a heating rate of 10 °C/min under a flow rate of 50 mL/min of nitrogen as the purge gas.

Self-Healed Polymer Testing:

Self-healed polymers (SHPs) were evaluated using a modified TDCB geometry to include a grooved short central trench (CT) section exclusively to contain the cured SHP [9]. SHP samples were prepared using precast CT sections, cured at 45 °C for 24 hours, with medium catalyst loading (Sc (M)). The precast SHP CT was placed in closed silicone moulds and the main geometry prepared from mixing 100 parts EPON 828 with 12 parts curing agent DETA into the mould and left to cure for 7 days at ambient temperature. A sharp

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razor blade was used to pre-crack cured samples prior to being pin-loaded on an Instron 3343 1 kN load cell at a displacement rate of $5 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$. Test specimens were cracked along the complete CT length until complete failure.

Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Composite Material Manufacture:

E-glass/epoxy (Hexply 913, Hexcel Composites) unidirectional (UD) plates (300 mm x 220 mm x 3.8 mm) were manufactured using hand lay-up (28 ply). Cure was undertaken according to the manufacturer's recommendations of 125°C for 1 hour and a pressure of 700 kPa. Stainless steel wire (ca. 0.5 mm in diameter) pre-coated with PTFE release agent was placed parallel to the fibre direction in pre-cut 0.5 mm channels (equal to the thickness of 4 plies) centred on the mid-plane.

Release film ($15 \mu\text{m}$ thickness) was placed from the laminate edge to 25 mm before the start of the vasculs. Cured composite plates were cut into DCB coupon specimens using a water-cooled diamond grit saw (195 mm x 20 mm x 3.8 mm). Piano hinges were bonded in place using Hexcel Redux 810 adhesive onto grit-blasted surfaces as preparation for mechanical testing.

Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Composite Material Testing:

An Instron 3343 fitted with a 1kN load cell was used to initiate and propagate Mode I crack opening. Double cantilever beam (DCB) E-glass composite test specimens fixed via attached piano hinges were loaded at a displacement rate of 2 mm/min in accordance with ASTM 5528-01 [27]. Cracks were propagated for 75 mm from the point of initiation and crack length recorded with a video camera.

Specimens were healed after initial fracture using the prescribed healing agent, delivery method and cure temperature (**Table 1**). SHAs were delivered via the edge-located vasculs using 26 gauge hypodermic needles. Healed specimens were re-tested as outlined above for initial fracture.

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Figure 1. DSC curves for E10 Sc (M), E25 Sc (M), E50 Sc (M), EPON Sc (M), EMIM25 Sc (M) and E12.5 EMIM12.5 Sc (M) samples.

Figure 2. Representative load-displacement curve for initial fracture of E10 Sc (M), E25 Sc (M) and EMIM EPA Sc (M) polymeric TDCB test specimens cured at 45 °C for 24 hours.

Figure 3. Double cantilever beam (DCB) Mode I specimen geometry. Note: all dimensions in mm; dashed lines represent internal features.

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Figure 4. Representative load-displacement curves for E10 Sc (M) DCB test specimens healed at 45 °C for 24 hours.

Figure 5. Representative load-displacement curves for E25 Sc (M) DCB test specimens healed at 45 °C for 24 hours.

Figure 6. Healing performance for maximum load.

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Table 1. DSC Data for E10 Metal Triflate Catalysts.

Designation	Heat of Reaction [J/g]	Onset Temperature [°C]	Maximum Temperature [°C]
E10 Sc (M)	337.9	34.6	129.2
E10 Al (M)	408.2	78.0	157.9
E10 Cu (M)	392.9	47.1	155.6

Table 2. Specimen derivatives used to demonstrate self-healing performance.

Designation	Monomer Solution ^{a)}	Catalyst	Catalyst Loading [pph] ^{b)}	Healing Temperature [°C]		
				45	80	RT
E10 Sc (M)	E10	Sc(OTf) ₃	3.125 (M)	X	X	X
E10 Al (M)		Al(OTf) ₃	3.125 (M)	X		
E25 Sc (M)	E25	Sc(OTf) ₃	3.125 (M)	X	X	X
E25 Sc (H)			6.25 (H)	X		X
E25 Sc (L)			1.5625 (L)	X		
EMIM EPA Sc (M)	E12.5 EMIM12.5		3.125 (M)	X		
AUTO EMIM EPA Sc (M)				X		
AUTO E25 Sc (M)	E25			X		
E25 Al (M)				Al(OTf) ₃	X	
E25 DETA		DETA	12			X

a) **E10**: 90 wt% EPON 828, 10 wt% Ethyl phenylacetate (EPA); **E25**: 75 wt% EPON 828, 25 wt% EPA.

E12.5 EMIM 12.5: 75 wt% EPON 828, 12.5 wt% EPA, 12.5 wt% EMIM BF₄

b) (L) = low loading, (M) = medium loading, (H) = high loading

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